

XFEM MODELLING OF TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The eXtended Finite Element Method (XFEM) allows modelling of multiple cracks in composite materials without prior knowledge of their positions and in a mesh independent way. In the present study we examine the XFEM implemented in ABAQUS for predictions of the onset and propagation of transverse cracks in cross-ply laminates under quasi-static tensile loading. The process of transverse cracking is a well understood phenomenon in composites and is used here to investigate the effect of numerical input parameters on the crack density predictions. The crack propagation is modelled using a linear cohesive law within XFEM. The model requires as input the transverse ply strength and intralaminar fracture toughness. The influence of these parameters is reported elsewhere. Among numerical parameters we examined the spacing between enriched regions and mesh size. The element size had no influence on the saturated crack density. The effect of the spacing was limited to small deviations in the crack density between initiation and saturation points.

1 INTRODUCTION

Damage in fibre-reinforced polymer composites develops on different scales and is linked to their internal structure. In case of cross-ply laminates subjected to longitudinal tensile load, damage starts as debondings at the fibre-matrix interface or microcracks in the matrix close to the interface. This first damage is triggered by stress concentrations due to the difference in transverse stiffness of the fibers and matrix. The debondings are then connected by a crack in the matrix thus forming a larger transverse crack at the meso-level, which also grows along the fibres. The number of transverse cracks increases with the applied load. At a certain level of the load the number of cracks reaches a saturation point, where no new cracks can be initiated in a ply. This process of cracking is well understood for both unidirectional and textile based polymer composites [1]. We selected this phenomenon for the current study to better understand the work, advantages and limitations of the XFEM in application to discrete damage modelling in composites.

Different techniques are available for modelling of progressive cracking. Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) is a popular approach for damage modelling [2, 3]. This methodology is proven to work well when the overall performance of the damaged material is of interest. The core idea of CDM

is to monitor the stress level and once it reaches a critical level the stiffness of the damaged region is degraded. Such an approach may, however, lead to predictions of unphysical damage zones, for example, zones which grow across the fibre direction [4]. To avoid this, new methods are required.

Recently, a group of methods has been developed based on the Partition of Unity concept [5, 6]. The eXtended Finite Element Method (XFEM) [7] has been used to model progressive damage in solids. In XFEM a crack is introduced within an existing mesh without a need to modify the mesh as the crack propagates. The crack is treated as a surface, which reflects discrete nature of damage in composites. The crack opening may be controlled by different mechanics, such as cohesive law or a virtual closure crack technique. The main advantage of the method is its ability to predict crack formation without prior assumptions on their position. XFEM has been applied in several works to investigate ply cracking in laminated composites using in-house developed codes. For example, Iarve et al. [8] utilized a modified version of XFEM for modelling of crack initiation and development in a laminate with an open hole; Van Der Meer et al. [9] modelled damage development in cross-ply laminates showing good agreement with experimentally measured crack densities.

In the present work, we explore the use of XFEM implemented in ABAQUS for studies of the initiation, development and saturation of transverse cracks in cross-ply laminates under tensile loading. The studies are performed in the absence of delaminations. The effect of delaminations will be reported elsewhere. A cohesive law-based XFEM for intra-ply damage is utilized. The model is designed to handle multiple cracks in a single ply.

Physical input parameters		
E_1	[GPa]	131
E_2	[GPa]	8.6
ν_{12}	–	0.32
ν_{23}	–	0.45
G_{12}	[GPa]	4.7
G_{32}	[GPa]	3
σ_{tr}	[MPa]	50
$G_{I\ cr}$	[J/m ²]	250

Table 1: Elastic parameters of a single ply, where E is Young's modulus, G is shear modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, σ_{tr} is transverse strength, $G_{I\ cr}$ is critical energy release rate for Mode I.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

The model geometry and input parameters are based on experimental investigations and data from literature [10, 11]. Thus, the cross-ply laminate under tensile load is used in the present analysis. The lay-up is $[0,0,90,90]_s$ and the thickness of a single ply is 0.12 mm in the laminate. Material properties of a single ply used in the simulations are listed in Table 1. The model requires input for the strength distribution of the transverse ply. The latter reflects failure phenomena on the micro-level that are sensitive to the distribution of fibres and defects. For, example, denser fibre packings lead to higher stress concentrations and are likely to promote an earlier onset of debonding at the fibre-matrix interface. The strength distribution influences crack formation on the meso-level. In the present work, a normal distribution of the transverse strength is utilized with a mean value given in Table 1 and a standard deviation of 15%. A maximum transverse stress criterion is selected for damage initiation. Damage evolution is described with a linear cohesive law, where softening of the traction is based on the mode-independent energy based criterion with the critical energy release rate listed in Table 1.

Figure 1: (a) Geometry of the laminate and boundary conditions, (b) illustration of the mesh.

The in-plane geometry of the laminate is 30 mm x 7.5 mm x 0.96 mm in length, width and thickness, respectively. The model is subjected to a longitudinal tensile displacement which is applied to face A (Figure 1a). The maximum displacement is equivalent to the applied strain of 1.8%. Face B and C (Figure 1a) are subjected to the symmetrical boundary conditions in the length and width directions, respectively. Other faces are traction free. The geometry is meshed with 300 elements in length, 30 elements in width and 16 elements through thickness directions.

Figure 2: Enrichment zones in the model (a) and extracted from the model (b); *Large Spacing* model with 50 enrichments (c), *Small Spacing* model with 100 enrichments.

XFEM in ABAQUS is used to model cracks in the transverse ply. An enriched zone (also referred to as “enrichment”) is assigned to the region where a crack may appear (Figure 2b), which allows the model to initiate and propagate an XFEM crack in this zone. To avoid limitations of the software several enrichments are assigned in the model, which allows multiple sites for crack initiation and propagation in the simulation (Figure 2a). These enrichments are evenly spaced by the distance, which is called “spacing” and given in millimetres. In the present work the influence of the spacing parameter is investigated. Thus, two different models are considered: “*Small Spacing*” with 0.3 mm smallest distance between the closest cracks and “*Large Spacing*” with 0.6 mm (Figure 2c,d). Other input parameters, such as the state of the random generator, the width of distribution, are fixed to constant values.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of the two simulations is done based on the crack density in function of the applied strain. The crack density is calculated as a number of cracks in the entire model divided by the length of the specimen. In the present work a crack is counted when it occupies one half of the specimen width. The same approach is used in the experimental work [10]. With the given spacing and dimensions of the laminate, the maximum crack density for *Large Spacing* model is limited to 3.3 cracks/mm, and for *Small Spacing* model to 1.6 cracks/mm.

There are two stages for the crack development in the model. The first stage corresponds to the formation of crack surfaces, and this happens at the moment when the transverse strength criterion has been fulfilled. These surfaces are still subjected to tractions and will undergo damage according to the specified cohesive law. The formed “defect” cannot be treated as a true crack in its physical sense and will be called here a “*Potential Crack*” (PC) to illustrate the number of crack initiation sites in the model. The final stage of the crack development is formation of traction-free surfaces. This stage corresponds to a more physical crack-like defect and may be compared to the experimentally observed cracks. These phases allow to calculate two different crack densities based on the algorithm described above. While the crack density shows the number of cracks, which are traction-free and can be compared with experiments, the potential crack density gives an idea how many cracks may still be opened if the applied strain would further increase. Both of these densities are used to compare results of the different models in this study.

Figure 3: Top: crack densities for modelling of *Large and Small Spacing* models; Bottom: transverse (across fibres) stress field plot in transverse ply with cracks.

The modelling results are shown on Figure 3. There are four curves plotted in total, two per each model. Crack density curves for PC show that the number of regions with initiated cracks is always higher in the *Spacing Small* model. This is reasonable because there are more enriched regions in the model. Many potential cracks are initiated in the model by the end of analysis. However, the number of traction-free cracks is the same for both models at the maximum strain level, which indicates that a system of transverse cracks is saturated and the stress level in-between of the traction-free cracks is not sufficient to trigger yet another one. At the same time, first traction-free cracks appear at the same level of applied strain in both models with large and small spacings. There is some deviation in cracks densities for these models in between the two points, initiation and saturation. The deviation can be explained by more weakened areas in *Small Spacing* model due to a higher number of potential cracks. The stress plot on Figure 3 shows the stress distribution due to the presence of cracks. There is a region with three cracks, where stress fields overlap. This may lead to defects that are still not traction-free by the end of analysis due to the stress release caused by adjacent cracks.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed model is capable to model a progressive cracking process in laminated composite materials. The model has shown to adequately predict the crack density curves in function of applied strain and which trend is similar to the experimental data found in literature.

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